

Role of silicon in plant disease management

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Abstract

Plant diseases are one of the crucial limiting factors that decrease crop production worldwide. Although chemicals can successfully manage diseases, the development of resistance and harmful reaction of chemicals on non-target organisms and the environment have raised global concerns towards the development of eco-friendly disease management strategies. Silicon (Si) is a good treatment to plant diseases and in the latest years a lot of work has been done on its use in managing plant diseases. Isenosuke onodera in 1917 first suggested that silicon was involved in resistance of rice against blast. As a result of experimentation from the 1914 until today, silicon's ability to decrease the disease intensity is now known for a large number of plants. After oxygen (49.2 %), silicon (25.7 %) is the element that is most prevalent in the lithosphere, commonly existing in the form non-available to the plants. Its uptake takes place through roots as silicic acid $[\text{Si}(\text{OH})_4]$ and has a positive effect on plant health by effectively reducing biotic and abiotic stresses (Ialam *et al.*, 2020). Silicon may be applied as root or foliar application (Zellner *et al.*, 2021). It's polymerization occurs in the extracellular spaces and accumulates on the walls of the epidermal cells of leaves and xylemvessels that acts as a physical barrier to hamper pathogen penetration. Plants benefit from silicon by having better mechanical and physiological qualities, which helps them withstand more biotic and abiotic challenges. Silicon can reduce plant disease through (a) preventing penetration of pathogen via physical barriers (b) antimicrobial chemical production as well as (c) stimulating defense-related gene expression and signaling pathway (Ahammed *et al.*, 2021). Therefore, Si application can contribute in the management of plant diseases, among other practices.

Keywords: chemical barrier, gene expression, Physical barrier, Silicon, Signalling pathway

INTRODUCTION

Plant diseases are one of the crucial limiting factors that decrease the crop production worldwide. Almost all crops are susceptible to diseases. According to an estimate, the crop loss due to disease is approximately 25 per cent per annum (Lugtenberg, 2015). At the local level such losses can have a huge economic impact and can lead to famine. Therefore, the well timed management of plant diseases must be given preference. Conventional management strategies involve the use of pesticides and cultural practices that include application of soil amendments for enhancing host plant resistance (Altieri, 2018). Although chemicals can effectively manage diseases, the development of resistance and harmful impact of chemicals on non-target organisms and the environment have raised global concerns towards the development of eco-friendly plant disease management strategies. This may include the application of various fertilizers (N, P and K) and elements such as zinc, boron, magnesium, and silicon. Silicon is a non-essential element for the growth and nutrition of plants (Arnon and Stout, 1939). However, recent research has discovered its function in reducing biotic and abiotic stresses in plants (Zargar *et al.*, 2019). After oxygen (49.2 %), silicon (25.7 %) is the element that is most prevalent in the lithosphere, commonly existing in the form non-available to the plants. Plants usually absorb silicon in the form of monosilicic acid (H_4SiO_4). In soil silicic acid concentration ranges between 0.1 to 0.6 mM. Soil solutions containing a pH lower than 9, are suitable for the absorption of H_4SiO_4 by plant roots (Paye *et al.*, 2018). Subsequently, the absorbed H_4SiO_4 polymerizes into silica gel in root intercellular spaces, cell walls and leaf cells (Mitani *et al.*, 2005). Absorption

of Si varies with plant species and genotype. Additionally, Si absorption capacity in plants is influenced by Si concentration in the soil and environmental conditions (Chen *et al.*, 2018). In general, poaceae plants absorb more Si compared to dicotyledonous plants (Ma and Yamaji, 2015). Several key agricultural benefits are associated with Si utilization such as rise in crop growth, production and productivity as well as refinement in soil structure (Walsh *et al.*, 2018). Silicon decreases the transpiration rate, stimulates enzyme activity and also reduces crop abiotic stress (Guo *et al.*, 2017). Plant diseases are a major trouble in agricultural production, resulting in a huge reduction in crop yield and quality. Silicon enhances tolerance against fungal, bacterial and viral pathogens of economically important crops (Song *et al.*, 2016). Isenosuke Onodera In 1917 first suggested that Si was involved in resistance of rice against blast pathogen. To date, there have been dozens of reports documenting Si's ability for enhancing resistance against fungal, bacterial, and viral plant diseases involving various modes of action. The objective of this review is to summarize and discuss the method of silicon application and its modes of action in management of various economically important plant diseases.

Sources of silicon

There are several solid and liquid sources of silicon that have been used as fertilizers or as soil amendments, for almost all the crops. For these materials to be useful, they must meet many criteria that include a relatively high soluble Si content, a physical state that will facilitate storage ability and ease of application, and they must contain negligible soil contaminants such as heavy metals (Gascho, 2001). Solid sources of silicon that have been used successfully include a naturally occurring mined calcium silicate Wollastonite, a byproduct of phosphate or steel industries of thermophosphate calcium silicate slag and cement (Tubana and heckman, 2015) and crop residues such as corn cob ash, rice husk, sugarcane waste, grasses, coconut husk, cow dung ash and wheat straw. However composition and concentration of silicon from these crop residues may not release at the same rate for meeting the plant's demand for the element when needed (Frsntz *et al.*, 2010). These solid silicon sources are applied as pre plant application @ 300 to 800 kg elemental silicon per hectare (Rodrigues *et al.*, 2015). Liquid sources of silicon include silica gel, monosilicic acid, calcium silicate, potassium silicate and sodium silicate that are used as a foliar spray or drench @100 ppm silicon depending on the silicon source.

More recently, silica nanoparticles have been shown to increase plant disease resistance (El-Shetehy *et al.*, 2021). Silica nanoparticles might prove to be another silicon source for future use in agriculture.

Table_1: List of silicon containing products

Product name	Product description
Sili-cal	Calcium silicate
Pro-Tekt	Potassium silicate solution
Plant Tuff	Calcium and magnesium silicates
Silixol	Orthosilicic acid
Sil-MATRIX	Potassium silicate
VansilW-10	Calcium metasilicate
CrossOver	Calcium and magnesium silicates

Methods of silicon application

Different sources of silicon can be applied both to the soil (root application) as well as to the foliage of the plant (foliar application) for suppressing crop diseases (Rodrigues *et al.*, 2015a). The root application provides efficient means of silicon absorption and distribution in the plant tissue. Foliar application of silicon has also been used for disease management. When the foliar application of silicon has been compared with root application, plants respond better to the latter. This comparison has been successfully demonstrated in the following different host-pathogen interactions: cucumber/ *Podosphaera xanthii* and *Erysiphe cichoracearum*, wheat/ *Blumeria graminis* f.sp. *tritici*, rice/*Magnaporthe oryzae* and rice/ *Bipolaris oryzae* (Cacique *et al.*, 2013). The mechanism by which silicon affects pathogen infection is dependent on whether it is applied to the soil or to the foliage. In case of root application, silicon moves continuously through the xylem vessels into root endodermis and cell membrane leading to its distribution throughout plant tissues. In case of root application several defence responses will be potentiated within the host plant while In case of foliar application silicon will quickly polymerize on the leaf surface to form a chemical-physical barrier, the most likely, the change in pH or the osmotic potential of the phyllosphere explain the reduction in development of some foliar diseases (Rodrigues *et al.*, 2015b).while little amount of silicon may drift through the cuticular matrix, more plausibly, the osmotic shift in the epidermal environment could induce silicon migration from the vascular tissue to other parts of the leaves. Although root application is consistently more effective than foliar application to suppress foliar diseases, the efficiency will be as such linked to the plant's capacity to absorb the silicon from the soil solution and accumulate high amounts in the shoots. However foliar application can still be used for many plant species infected by different pathogens. Sill the effectiveness for disease management may depend on the application frequency, the environmental conditions, the lifestyle of the pathogen and its aggressiveness level, as well as the inoculum amount produced during the infection period (Andrade *et al.*, 2013). For instance liquid sources are quickly depleted from the environment either

due to the plant absorption or leaching from the root zone. The phloem limited movement of silicon requires continuous supply so that newly emerging tissues can be efficiently protected. This explains why liquid sources need multiple applications throughout the life cycle of plant. In case of solid sources, the continuous release into the root zone occurs throughout the crop growing season. Some products, such as calcium silicate slags, may have a residual effect of three years after the initial soil amendment.

Mode of action

1) Physical mechanism

The basic concept of physical mechanism is the formation of a mechanical hindrance through Si accumulation below the cuticle and in cell walls that stop or delay the penetration of infection pegs of pathogen appressoria (Fig. 1). In addition to the formation of the Si-enriched layer, the uniform distribution of Si aggregates is critical to effectively prevent pathogen ingress (Wang *et al.*, 2017). This hypothesis was first introduced to explain the Si-induced suppression of rice blast disease, which was subsequently accepted as a potential mechanism of Si-induced minimization of disease intensity in many plant species (Rodrigues *et al.*, 2015). For example, high Si deposition in the epidermal cell walls creates a physical barrier in barley leaves, which largely blocks appressoria penetration of *Blumeria graminis* f. sp. *hordei* (Debona *et al.*, 2017). Notably, non-uniform or too scattered Si deposition below the cuticle and cell wall may not totally prevent penetration of pathogen, but to some extent can delay incubation/latent period of pathogen. Thus, the physical barriers due to the silicification of the leaf epidermal cell walls not only reduce pathogen penetration, but also delay the pathogen penetration, colonization and inoculum production or sporulation in many host-pathogen interactions. Even though penetration of pathogen may occur under certain circumstances, its growth such as formation of haustoria is largely inhibited by Si-stimulated papillae formation and accumulation of phenolic compounds in leaves (Hawerth *et al.*, 2018). The Si can even boost the resistance of a susceptible cultivar to the level of a resistant cultivar against a specific pathogen (Resende *et al.*, 2013). Notably, accumulation of silicon also occurs in endodermal cells of root (Lux *et al.*, 2020). Silicon application increases cucumber resistance against *F. oxysporum* f.sp. *cucumerinum* causing wilt disease (Zhou *et al.*, 2018). Although enhancement of mechanical properties of root tissue by silicification has been attributed to the easing of soil penetration by roots, less attention has been paid to understanding the role of Si accumulation in increasing resistance against root diseases. In sorghum, root cell wall modifications by Si application can suppress the invasion of *Alternaria alternata* (Bathoova *et al.*, 2018). Thus similar to Si accumulation in foliar tissues, silicification-induced improved mechanical properties may also play a role in enhancing resistance against root diseases. However, studies have also revealed that during pathogen entry soluble Si can be more important than insoluble Si, indicating the much more important role of Si in lowering the disease severity beyond physical barriers (Ratnayake *et al.*, 2016). Thus, Si-induced suppression of disease development is attributed to yet unknown complex physiological, biochemical and molecular mechanisms.

Fig.1. Silicon possesses anti-pathogenic properties and minimizes foliar disease development by the formation of physical barriers. (A) In vitro antifungal activity of Si, (B) Hypothetical leaf phenotypes showing suppression of lesion

growth by Si application in vivo, and (C) Classical concept of physical barrier hypothesis showing the formation of insoluble silicon layer that prevents penetration of fungi.

2) Biochemical mechanism

Silicon induced biochemical resistance is associated with;

- a) Increase in the activity of defence related enzymes.
- b) Inducing antimicrobial compounds production.
- c) Regulating systemic signal that is salicylic acid signalling pathway.

a) Defence-Related Enzymes

In plant-pathogen interactions, Si has been observed to increase the activity of defense-related enzymes, which are strongly associated to disease resistance (Van et al., 2013). The activation of defence-related enzyme activities by Si including chitinase, peroxidases, polyphenoloxidases, beta-1, 3-glucanase, phenylalanine ammonia-lyase, superoxide dismutase, ascorbate peroxidase, glutathione reductase, catalase, lipoxygenase, and glucanase have been reported in several studies. Plant disease resistance responses depend on PAL, which is involved in the manufacture of secondary antimicrobial compounds (Waewthongrak et al., 2015). The greater PAL activity following Si treatment causes the leaves of banana and coffee plants to accumulate more total soluble phenolic and lignin-thioglycolic acid derivatives, which is correlated with low disease incidence (Fortunato et al., 2012b). The primary enzyme for phenolic substance oxidation is Polyphenol oxidase (PPO), which primarily found in cytoplasm in a free form or bound in chloroplasts, mitochondria, and other subcellular organelles (Quarta et al., 2013); its activity has been positively correlated with plant disease resistance (Piperno, 2006). PPO was also discovered to be involved in lignin formation and to improve the host plant's capacity to fight bacteria (Song et al., 2016). Si treatment may also boost the activity of enzymes peroxidase (POD) and chitinase (CHT), which are crucial in host-pathogen interactions. POD is involved in cell-wall strengthening, the last stage of lignin production and the cross-linking of cell-wall proteins, whereas CHT is one of the PR proteins that help to hydrolyze the cell walls of many phytopathogenic fungi. Defense-related enzyme activities induced by Si may regulate gene expression related to enzyme synthesis; for example, the expression of genes encoding phenylalanine ammonia-lyase (PALa and PALb) and lipoxygenase (LOXa) were significantly up-regulated in Si-treated perennial ryegrass plants, which was associated with suppression of gray leaf spot (Rahman et al., 2015). Si potentially increases the activities of defence-related enzymes (like peroxidase and polyphenol oxidase) via enhancing or priming JA-inducible responses to herbivory in rice (Ye et al., 2013). Si has been shown to be helpful for suppressing pathogen infections by increasing the activities of defence related enzymes in the pathosystems of cucumber (*Pythium* spp. and *Podosphaera xanthii*), pea (*Mycosphaerella pinodes*), wheat (*Pyricularia oryzae*), rice (*Magnaporthe oryzae*, *Bipolaris oryzae*, *Rhizoctonia solani*, and *Pyricularia oryzae*), melon (*Trichothecium roseum* and *Podosphaera xanthii*), bean (*Colletotrichum lindemuthianum*), perennial ryegrass (*Magnaporthe oryzae*), and soybean (*Corynespora cassiicola*).

b) Antimicrobial compound

The production and accumulation of antimicrobial compounds, such as phenols, flavonoids, phytoalexins, and PR proteins in plants after pathogen penetration are caused by defence-related enzyme activity. Generally, lower disease incidence in plants after Si application is associated with a higher activity of these enzymes (Remus-Borel *et al.*, 2005). In contrast, the application of Si had the reverse impact in soybeans, increasing the host's sensitivity to frog eye leaf spot by reducing the baseline antioxidant enzyme activity of leaves during *Cercospora sojina* infection. These results imply that Si-induced plant disease resistance was most likely due to the suboptimal antioxidant system conditioning (Telles Nascimento *et al.*, 2016). Antimicrobial compounds aid higher plants in fighting disease (Van *et al.*, 2013), moreover during pathogen infection, Si has been shown to induce the accumulation of antimicrobial substances, such as phenols, flavonoids, and phytoalexins during pathogen infection (Remus-Borel *et al.*, 2005), this may thus contribute to the improvement of defence-related enzyme activities. Following pathogen invasion, PAL and PPO inducing activities led to the production of defence-related antimicrobial phenols or lignin-associated polyphenolic compounds that were boosted by Si (Rahman *et al.*, 2015). Si increased PAL activity, which in turn transforms L-phenylalanine into trans-cinnamic acid, the precursor of lignin and flavonoids, is thought to be the cause of the increased lignin and flavonoid production (Hao *et al.*, 2011). The secondary metabolism of Lignin and phenols are crucial for plant disease resistance. In plant cell walls, Si has a role in lignin production and phenolic metabolism (Marschner, 2012). Additionally it raises the amount of lignin and lignin-carbohydrate complexes in the epidermal cell wall and improves rice plant resistance to blast disease (Cai *et al.*, 2008). Si supply could raise the total content of soluble phenolic substances in host plants and improve plant disease resistance through delaying the growth of invading pathogens (Fortunato *et al.*, 2015). Si also induces flavonoid production, another phenolic molecule, which increases wheat resistance to *Pyricularia oryzae* (Silva *et al.*, 2015) and rose plant resistance to *Podosphaera pannosa* (Shetty *et al.*, 2012). Si treatment increased the accumulation of phenolic and lignin or ligninthioglycolic acid derivatives which strengthened cucumber plants against damping-off caused by *Pythium ultimum*, wheat against powdery mildew caused by *Blumeria graminis* (Belanger *et al.*, 2003) and blast caused by *Pyricularia oryzae* (Filha *et al.*, 2011), *Arabidopsis* against powdery mildew caused by *Erysiphe cichoracearum* (Ghanmi *et al.*, 2004), soybean against target spot caused by *Corynespora cassiicola* (Fortunato *et al.*, 2015), melon against powdery mildew caused by *Podosphaera xanthii* (Dallagnol *et al.*, 2015), rice against blast disease caused by

Magnaporthe grisea (Cai *et al.*, 2008), brown spot caused by *Bipolaris oryzae* (Dallagnol *et al.*, 2011), and sheath blight caused by *Rhizoctonia solani* (Zhang *et al.*, 2013). It is well known that phytoalexins play a key role in plant defence against pathogen infection. The prevalence of powdery mildew caused by *Podosphaera xanthii* in cucumber plants and blast caused by *M. grisea* in rice is decreased by increasing the production of phytoalexins (Rodrigues *et al.*, 2005). According to reports, Si supply during *Podosphaera xanthii* infection causes cucumber plants to accumulate more flavonoid phytoalexins. Similar findings were made with rice, where Si improved blast resistance by promoting the formation of phytoalexins, such as momilactones A and B (Rodrigues *et al.*, 2005). Si-induced elevation of phenolic acids, such as chlorogenic acid and flavonoids, as well as relative levels of genes encoding PAL and lipoxygenase in perennial ryegrass-*Magnaporthe oryzae* pathosystems improved resistance to gray leaf spot (Rahman *et al.*, 2015).

c) Systemic signal

Host plants have evolved a complex immune system that provides multiple layers of constitutive and inducible defence mechanisms. This immune system is controlled by a complex network of signal transduction pathways (Grant *et al.*, 2013). SA is essential for the plant immunity networks and defence mechanisms (Devadas *et al.*, 2002). Pathogens that are biotrophic and hemibiotrophic are the principal targets of SA (Pieterse *et al.*, 2012). According to several studies, Si may control phytohormone homeostasis and signalling pathways to control plant stress responses (Reynolds *et al.*, 2016). In response to pathogen invasion, plant phytohormones built up in Si-treated plants (Kim *et al.*, 2014). The biosynthesis of SA in leaves was accelerated in Si-treated *Arabidopsis* plants that were infected with powdery mildew pathogen, *Erysiphe cichoracearum* increasing their resistance (Fauteux *et al.*, 2006). Si increases the expression of genes encoding enzymes involved in the SA pathway in the defence of *Arabidopsis* against powdery mildew but resistant phenotypes show a significantly lower production of SA and expression of defence genes compared to susceptible controls, suggesting that Si-mediated resistance involves mechanisms other than SA-dependent defence responses (Vivancos *et al.*, 2015). Figure 2 illustrates the signaling cascade in the Si-regulated plant defence response. The EDS1 and PAD4 genes are necessary for the synthesis of SA, whereas the EDS5 and SID2 genes play a role in controlling the production of SA (Shah, 2003). The TaLsi plant, in *Arabidopsis* which contained higher Si were more resistant to *Golovinomyces cichoracearum* infection compared to control plants when treated with Si, and this increased resistance was accompanied by higher expressions of EDS1 and PAD4 genes, as well as NPR1 and three SA-induced PR defence genes PR1, PR2, and PR5 (Vivancos *et al.*, 2015). Additionally, the TaLsi1 sid2 and TaLsi1 pad4 mutants, which crossed mutants pad4 and sid2 with the line TaLsi1, displayed smaller area under the disease progress curve (AUDPC) following Si supply, indicating that Si-enhanced resistance to *Golovinomyces cichoracearum* infection in *Arabidopsis* is maintained in pad4 and sid2 mutants engineered to better absorb Si (Vivancos *et al.*, 2015). The regulatory protein NPR1, which is positively controlled by several SA-inducible WRKY proteins is essential for the activation of PR gene expression in response to SA (Li *et al.*, 2004). The gene expression of transcription factor WRKY1 was increased during tomato plant infected with *R. solanacearum* in response to Si (Ghareeb *et al.*, 2011). The SA dependent pathway, which is accompanied by an increase in the amount of endogenous SA and subsequent by expression of PRs is responsible for the Si-induced induction of defence related genes and transcripts (Kurabachew *et al.*, 2013).

Fig. 2: Signalling system that silicon controls during the plant defence response.

3) Molecular Mechanism

Through a series of physiological and biochemical and signal transduction mechanisms, silicon is engaged in the metabolic processes of plant–pathogen interaction, activating host plant defence genes and triggering a resistance response in plants to prevent plant diseases (Vivancos *et al.*, 2015). Si may influence the activity of post-elicitation intracellular signalling systems which control the expression of defence genes involved in cell wall modifications, hypersensitivity reactions, hormone synthesis, antimicrobial compound synthesis, and PR proteins (Fauteux *et al.*, 2005). Studies in transcriptomic and proteomic have been carried out to demonstrate the defence responses of Si in various pathosystems (Ghareeb *et al.*, 2011). By increasing the expression of defence and stress responses genes such as WRKY1 transcription factor, disease resistance response protein, ferritin, late embryogenesis abundant protein, and trehalose phosphatase, Si may be able to make tomato plants resistant to *Ralstonia solanacearum* (Ghareeb *et al.*, 2011). Similar result were observed in tomato stems of rhizobacteria and silicon treated-tomato genotypes after infection with *R. solanacearum* compared to the non-treated, pathogen inoculated control, in which most of the up-regulated genes are involved in signal transduction, defence, protein synthesis and metabolism and the majority of down regulated genes were involved in photosynthesis and lipid metabolism (Kurabachew *et al.*, 2013). The expression of gene encoding a new proline-rich protein (PRP1) was increased, during the induction of systemic acquired resistance in cucumber mediated with Si which helped to fortify cell-walls when fungi tried to enter epidermal cells (Kauss *et al.*, 2003). The expression of chitinase-II, glucanase and peroxydase, which are attributed to virulence factors released by the pathogen to inhibit host resistance and facilitate host invasion, were down-regulated by Si application during *R. solanacearum* interactions in tomato plants (Ghareeb *et al.*, 2011). 26 proteins were significantly altered by Si supply in tomato plants inoculated with *R. solanacearum*, indicating that Si-mediated disease resistance may be connected to change in proteins (Chen *et al.*, 2014). Silicon can reverse many transcriptional changes brought on by pathogen infection, for instance, when *Arabidopsis* is infected with the *Erysiphe cichoracearum*, the expression of nearly 4000 genes is altered. In comparison to control and Si-treated plants, the number of up-regulated defence related genes did not change, while the magnitude of down-regulated, primary metabolism-related genes was attenuated (Fauteux *et al.*, 2006). About 900 genes responding to pathogen infection were altered in control leaves of wheat plants infected with *Blumeria graminis* f. sp. tritici but only a small number of genes were altered by the pathogen in Si-supplied plants, indicating that Si almost eliminated the stress imposed by the pathogen invasion (Chain *et al.*, 2009). The impact of *Magnaporthe oryzae* inoculation on the transcriptome of rice is lessened by Si treatment according to research by Brunings *et al.*, 2009. Si appears to eliminate the effects of pathogen infection on the transcriptome of host plants, perhaps by inhibiting the exploitation of pathogen virulence factors, rather than inducing resistance by transcriptional reprogramming of defence-related genes (Van *et al.*, 2015).

Table_1: Effects of silicon on plant disease

Hosts	Diseases	Pathogens	Effects	Reference	Resistance mechanisms
<i>Arabidopsis</i>	Powdery mildew	<i>Erysiphe cichoracearum</i> , <i>Agrobacterium tumefaciens</i>	+	Ghanmi <i>et al.</i> , 2004; Fauteux <i>et al.</i> , 2006; Vivancos <i>et al.</i> , 2015	Physical, biochemical and molecular
Banana	Black sigatoka	<i>Mycosphaerella fijiensis</i>	+	Kablan <i>et al.</i> , 2012	Physical and biochemical
	Fusarium wilt	<i>Fusarium oxysporum</i> f. sp. <i>cubense</i>	+	Fortunato <i>et al.</i> , 2012a	Physical and biochemical
	Root rot	<i>Cylindrocladium spathiphylli</i>	+	Vermeire <i>et al.</i> , 2011	Biochemical
	Xanthomonas wilt	<i>Xanthomonas campestris</i>	+	Mburu <i>et al.</i> , 2015	Physical and biochemical
Barley	Powdery mildew	<i>Blumeria graminis</i>	+	Wiese <i>et al.</i> , 2005	Physical
Bean	Angular leaf spot	<i>Pseudocercospora griseola</i>	+	Rodríguez <i>et al.</i> , 2010	Physical
Belle pepper	Phytophthora blight	<i>Phytophthora capsici</i>	+	French-Monar <i>et al.</i> , 2010	Physical
Bentgrass	Dollar spot	<i>Sclerotinia homoeocarpa</i>	+	Uriarte <i>et al.</i> , 2004; Zhang <i>et al.</i> , 2006	Physical and biochemical ?
Bitter melon	Powdery mildew	<i>Erysiphe</i> sp.	+	Ratnayake <i>et al.</i> , 2016	Biochemical
Capsicum	Anthraxnose	<i>Colletotrichum gloeosporioides</i>	+	Jayawardana <i>et al.</i> , 2016	Physical and biochemical
Cherry	Fruit decay	<i>Penicillium expansum</i> , <i>Monilinia fructicola</i>	+	Qin and Tian, 2005	Biochemical
Chinese cantaloupe	Fusarium root rot	<i>Fusarium</i> spp.	+	Liu <i>et al.</i> , 2009	Physical and biochemical
	Postharvest pink rot	<i>Trichothecium roseum</i>	+	Guo <i>et al.</i> , 2007	Physical and biochemical
Coffee	Leaf rust	<i>Hemileia vastatrix</i>	+	Carré-Missio <i>et al.</i> , 2014	Physical
	Root-knot Nematode	<i>Meloidogyne exigua</i>	+	Silva R. <i>et al.</i> , 2010	Biochemical
Common bean	Anthraxnose	<i>Colletotrichum lindemuthianum</i>	+	Polanco <i>et al.</i> , 2014; Rodríguez <i>et al.</i> , 2015a	Biochemical
Cotton	Fusarium wilt	<i>Fusarium oxysporum</i> f. sp. <i>vasinfectum</i>	+	Whan <i>et al.</i> , 2016	Physical and biochemical
Creeping, turf grass	Brown patch	<i>Rhizoctonia solani</i>	+	Uriarte <i>et al.</i> , 2004; Zhang <i>et al.</i> , 2006	Physical and biochemical?
Cucumber	Crown and root rot	<i>Pythium ultimum</i>	+	Chérif <i>et al.</i> , 1994	Biochemical
	Fusarium wilt	<i>Fusarium oxysporum</i> f. sp. <i>cucumerinum</i>	+	Miyake and Takahashi, 1983	Physical and biochemical?
	Powdery mildew	<i>Sphaerotheca fuliginea</i> , <i>Podosphaera xanthii</i>	+	Menzies <i>et al.</i> , 1991, 1992; Fawe <i>et al.</i> , 1998; Liang <i>et al.</i> , 2005a	Physical and biochemical

Hami melons	Decay	<i>Alternaria alternate</i> , <i>Fusarium semitectum</i> , <i>Trichothecium roseum</i>	+	Bi et al., 2006	Biochemical
Lettuce	Downy mildew	<i>Bremia lactucae</i>	+	Garibaldi et al., 2011	Physical and biochemical?
Melon	Bacterial fruit blotch	<i>Acidovorax citrulli</i>	+	Conceição et al., 2014	Biochemical
	Powdery mildew	<i>Podosphaera xanthii</i>	+	Dallagnol et al., 2015	Biochemical
Muskmelon	Pink rot disease	<i>Trichothecium roseum</i>	+	Li et al., 2011	Biochemical
	Powdery mildew	<i>Sphaerotheca fulginea</i>	+	Menzies et al., 1992	Physical and biochemical
Oil palm	Basal stem rot	<i>Ganoderma boninense</i>	+	Najjah et al., 2015	Physical
Pea	Brown spot	<i>Mycosphaerella pinodes</i>	+	Dann and Muir, 2002	Biochemical
Pearl millet	Downy mildew	<i>Sclerospora graminicola</i>	+	Deepak et al., 2008	Physical and biochemical
Perennial ryegrass	Fusarium patch	<i>Microdochium nivale</i>	+	McDonagh and Hunter, 2010	Physical
	Gray leaf spot	<i>Magnaporthe oryzae</i>	+	Rahman et al., 2015	Biochemical
Potato	Dry rot	<i>Fusarium sulphureum</i>	+	Li et al., 2009	Biochemical
Pumpkin	Powdery mildew	<i>Podosphaera xanthii</i>	+	Lepolu Torton et al., 2016	Physical and biochemical?
Rice	Blast	<i>Pyricularia oryzae</i> , <i>Magnaporthe grisea</i> , <i>Magnaporthe oryzae</i>	+	Seebold et al., 2000; Kim et al., 2002; Rodrigues et al., 2003; Cai et al., 2008, Hayasaka et al., 2008; Brunings et al., 2009; Domiciano et al., 2015	Physical, biochemical and molecular

Hosts	Diseases	Pathogens	Effects	Reference	Resistance mechanisms
	Brown spot	<i>Bipolaris oryzae</i> , <i>Cochliobolus miyabeanus</i>	+	Dallagnol et al., 2011, 2013; Prabhu et al., 2012; Van et al., 2015a	Physical, biochemical and molecular
	Grain discoloration	<i>Bipolaris oryzae</i>	+	Prabhu et al., 2012	Molecular
	Leaf scald	<i>Monographella albescens</i> , <i>Microdochium oryzae</i>	+	Tatagiba et al., 2016; Araujo et al., 2015	Physical and biochemical
	Sheath blight	<i>Rhizoctonia solani</i>	+	Peters et al., 2001; Schurt et al., 2014	Physical and biochemical
Rose	Powdery mildew	<i>Podosphaera pannosa</i>	+	Shetty et al., 2012	Physical
Sorghum	Anthraxnose	<i>Colletotrichum sublineolum</i>	+	Resende et al., 2013	Physical and biochemical ?
Soybean	Phytophthora stem and root rot	<i>Phytophthora sojae</i>	+	Guérin et al., 2014	Molecular
	Rust	<i>Phakopsora pachyrhizi</i>	+	Cruz et al., 2014; Lemes et al., 2011	Biochemical
St. Augustinegrass	Gray leaf spot	<i>Magnaporthe grisea</i>	+	Brecht et al., 2007	Physical and biochemical
Strawberry	Powdery mildew	<i>Sphaerotheca aphanis</i>	+	Kanto et al., 2006	Physical and biochemical
Sugarcane	Brown rust	<i>Puccinia melanocephala</i>	+	Ramouthar et al., 2015	Physical and biochemical ?
Tall fescue	Brown patch	<i>Rhizoctonia solani</i>	-	Zhang et al., 2006	/
Tobacco	Viral infection	<i>Tobacco ringspot virus</i> <i>Tobacco mosaic virus</i>	+/	Zellner et al., 2011 Zellner et al., 2011	Molecular /
Tomato	Bacterial speck	<i>Pseudomonas syringae</i>	+	Andrade et al., 2013	Biochemical
	Bacterial wilt	<i>Ralstonia solanacearum</i>	+	Ghareeb et al., 2011; Chen et al., 2014	Molecular
	Fusarium crown and root rot	<i>Fusarium oxysporum</i> f. sp <i>radicis-lycopersici</i>	+	Huang et al., 2011	Physical
Tomato, bitter gourd	Root rot	<i>Pythium aphanidermatum</i>	+	Heine et al., 2007	Biochemical and molecular?
Wheat	Blast	<i>Pyricularia grisea</i>	+	Filha et al., 2011	Physical and biochemical
	Leaf blast	<i>Pyricularia oryzae</i>	+	Silva et al., 2015	Biochemical
	Leaf streak	<i>Xanthomonas translucens</i>	+	Silva I.T. et al., 2010	Physical and biochemical
	Powdery mildew	<i>Blumeria graminis</i>	+	Chain et al., 2009; Guével et al., 2007; Moldes et al., 2016	Physical, biochemical and molecular
	Spot blotch	<i>Bipolaris sorokiniana</i>	+	Domiciano et al., 2010	Physical and biochemical
Zucchini squash	Powdery mildew	<i>Erysiphe cichoracearum</i> , <i>Podosphaera xanthii</i>	+	Menzies et al., 1992; Savvas et al., 2009	Physical and biochemical

Case study-1

The Role of Silicon in Preventing Appressorial Penetration by the Rice Blast Fungus

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Objective: To test the penetration resistance hypothesis - Application of silicon to rice will confer resistance to leaf epidermal cells against appressorial penetration by *Magnaporthe oryzae*.

RESULTS

Disease severity of leaf blast, assessed as the number of lesions per leaf, decreased with increasing rate of silica gel applied to the rice plants in experiment 1. This tendency was observed for all wet period durations between 8 and 20 h after spray inoculation. Leaf blast severity increased as the length of wet period increased for all rates of silica gel applied. ANOVA indicated that the effect of silica gel applied and the effect of the wet period on the number of leaf blast lesions were both statistically significant ($P < 0.0001$), and the interaction between these two factors were also significant ($P = 0.0004$). The amount of Si contained in the eighth leaf increased with increasing rates of applied silica gel to the rice plants and was consistent for all the experiments. The mean density of appressoria on motor cells was 332 cm^{-2} , with the standard deviation 69.1 cm^{-2} . ANOVA showed that there were no significant differences in frequency of appressoria forming due to the rate of silica gel applied ($P = 0.253$), the length of wet period (relative humidity over 99%) after spray inoculation ($P = 0.685$), and replication of the seedling boxes ($P = 0.451$). Some appressoria penetrated the epidermal cells of the rice leaves. The mean number of appressoria observed under the same amount of silica gel applied and the same length of wet period after inoculation was 2,391.2 with the standard deviation 258.5. The proportion of penetrated appressoria to total appressoria was reduced with an increasing rate of silica gel applied to rice, regardless of the length of wet period after inoculation, and was statistically significant based on the Cochran-Armitage test ($P < 0.001$) (1). The proportions of penetrated appressoria to total appressoria also increased with the length of the wet period regardless of the rate of silica gel applied, and was also statistically significant based on the Cochran-Armitage test ($P < 0.001$). Both the number of lesions per leaf and the proportion of penetrated appressoria decreased with the amount of Si applied. However, only a relatively small portion of the penetrated appressoria developed to become sporulating lesions (approximately 10 to 65% depending on experiment). As Si amount increased from 0 to 0.8 g, the proportion of appressoria that penetrated the epidermis after 111 h decreased 5-fold, while the proportion of penetration that progressed to sporulating lesions fell only 2.5-fold.

Case study-2

Physiological and Biochemical Aspects of the Resistance of Banana Plants to Fusarium Wilt Potentiated by Silicon

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Objective: To investigate whether Si could affect physiological and biochemical events in the banana–*F. oxysporum* f. sp. *cube* interaction (Fortunato *et al.*, 2021).

RESULTS

The factors Si rate and cultivar and their interaction were significant for relative lesion length (RLL). The +Si plants from Grand Nain and “Maçã” showed significant reductions of 40.0 and 57.2 per cent, respectively, for RLL compared with –Si plants. A significant difference was found between –Si plants of Grand Nain and “Maçã”. The RLL was significantly reduced by 37.8 per cent in the –Si plants of Grand Nain compared with “Maçã.”

TABLE 2. Relative lesion length (RLL) on banana plants from Grand Nain and “Maçã” grown in soil amended (+Si) or nonamended (–Si) with silicon and inoculated with *Fusarium oxysporum* f. sp. *cube* race 1²

Treatments	RLL (%)	
	Grand Nain	“Maçã”
–Si	11.31 Ab	18.19 Aa
+Si	6.79 Ba	7.78 Ba

The Si rate, cultivar, and sampling time were significant. The TSP concentration significantly increased by 20.80, 8.92, and 24.65 per cent at 0 h (noninoculated roots), 72, and 120 hai, respectively, for +Si plants of Grand Nain compared with –Si plants. Significant increases of 46.1, 29.9, and 19.2 per cent at 0 h (noninoculated roots), 72, and 120 hai, respectively, occurred in the +Si plants of “Maçã” compared with –Si plants.

Fig. 3. Concentration of total soluble phenolics (TSP) on roots of plants from Grand Nain and “Maçã” grown in soil amended (+Si) or nonamended (–Si) with silicon (Si) at different times after inoculation with *Fusarium oxysporum*

The factor Si rate was significant for the five enzymes studied. The cultivar was significant only for PPOs activity Table 4. The sampling time was significant only for the PALs, POXs, and CHIs activities. For PALs and PPOs, the only significant interaction was cultivar–sampling time. The PALs and PPOs activities were significantly higher at 24–120 hai in the +Si plants of Grand Nain and “Maçã” compared with –Si plants. No significant difference was found between the –Si and +Si plants of Grand Nain and “Maçã” noninoculated with *F. oxysporum* f. sp. *Cubense*. The POXs activity was significantly higher at 24, 48, 72, and 96 hai for +Si plants of Grand Nain compared with –Si plants. For +Si plants of “Maçã”, the POXs activity was significantly higher at 24, 48, 96, and 120 hai compared with –Si plants. No significant difference was found between the –Si and +Si plants of Grand Nain and “Maçã” noninoculated with *F. oxysporum* f. sp. *Cubense* (0 h). The GLUs activity was significantly higher at 0 h (noninoculated roots), 24, 48, and 96 hai for plants of Grand Nain and at 24, 48, 72, and 96 hai for plants of “Maçã” supplied with Si than for nonsupplied ones. No significant difference was found between the –Si and +Si plants of Grand Nain at 72 hai. No significant difference was found between the –Si and +Si plants of “Maçã” noninoculated with *F. oxysporum* f. sp. *Cubense* (0 h) and at 120 hai. The QUI activity was significantly higher for +Si plants of Grand Nain and “Maçã” from 24 to 120 hai compared with –Si plants. No significant difference was found between the –Si and +Si plants of Grand Nain and “Maçã” noninoculated with *F. oxysporum* f. sp. *Cubense* (0 h).

Fig. 5. Phenylalanine ammonia-lyase (PAL) activity on roots of plants from **A**, Grand Nain and **B**, “Maçã” grown in soil amended (+Si) or nonamended (–Si) with silicon (Si) at different times after inoculation with *Fusarium oxy-*

Fig. 7. Peroxidase (POX) activity on roots of plants from **A**, Grand Nain and **B**, "Maçã" grown in soil amended (+Si) or nonamended (-Si) with silicon (Si) at different times after inoculation with *Fusarium oxysporum* f. sp. *cubense*

Fig. 6. Polyphenoloxidase (PPO) activity on roots of plants from **A**, Grand Nain and **B**, "Maçã" grown in soil amended (+Si) or nonamended (-Si) with silicon (Si) at different times after inoculation with *Fusarium oxysporum* f. sp. *cubense*

Fig. 8. β -1,3-Glucanase (GLU) activity on roots of plants from **A**, Grand Nain and **B**, “Maçã” grown in soil amended (+Si) or nonamended (–Si) with silicon (Si) at different times after inoculation with *Fusarium oxysporum* f. sp.

Case study-3

Effect of root and foliar applications of soluble silicon on powdery mildew control and growth of wheat plants

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Objectives: To evaluate the prophylactic role of different Si formulations (Guevel *et al.*, 2017).

RESULTS

Treatment of wheat plants with the Kasil and Silamol solutions in the soil resulted in a significant reduction of powdery mildew severity compared to the MRD-250 and the control. As expected, Kasil provided a good control of the disease at a time where control plants had high levels of infection. Interestingly, Silamol, a product formulated for foliar applications, also yielded excellent control of powdery mildew, comparable to that of Kasil, when used as a soil drench at 1.7 mM Si. The MRD-250 treatment, for which applied Si concentration was lower (0.9 mM vs 1.7 mM) than the other Si treatments because of solubility issues, gave a lower disease control than Kasil and Silamol but nevertheless resulted in a lower powdery mildew severity than the control. Foliar applications of Si and control solutions gave varying levels of powdery mildew control on wheat plants. From the onset, the application of foliar sprays caused a significant reduction of powdery mildew compared to plants receiving no foliar treatment. Hoagland’s solution resulted in a similar disease control as the Si-based products. In our experiments, all three Si-based products applied as a foliar solution performed equally well even though the concentration in Si varied among the products. In fact, in preliminary trials, Silamol was as effective at 0.3 mM as at 1.7 mM in foliar sprays. The water foliar spray was not significantly different from the MRD-250, but was significantly less effective than the other foliar sprays. The severity of powdery mildew on the MRD-250 foliar spray-treated plants was not significantly different to powdery mildew severity on plants receiving the other foliar spray treatments.

Fig. 2 Severity of powdery mildew, caused by *Blumeria graminis* f. sp *tritici* on wheat plants fed with different silicon-based solutions amended to the soil. Silicon and formulation effects on powdery mildew severity were evaluated. Means followed by the same letter are not significantly different according to LS mean differences Student's *t* ($\alpha=0.05$)

Fig. 3 Severity of powdery mildew, caused by *Blumeria graminis* f. sp *tritici* on wheat plants receiving foliar applications of different silicon-based solutions (Kasil, Silamol and MRD-250), Hoagland's solution, water and a control treatment without foliar application. Means followed by the same letter are not significantly different according to LS mean differences Student's *t* ($\alpha=0.05$)

CONCLUSION

- Si induces resistance to both foliar and root diseases in many crops.
- In addition to the formation of Si-enriched physical barriers, Si treatment restricts pathogen proliferation by boosting distinct defence responses, such as deposition of phenolic compounds, phytoalexin production, and expression of pathogenesis-related proteins.
- Silicon also has a direct role in molecular defence-associated signalling pathway.
- Different kinds of Si fertilizers that come from both organic (rice husk, wheat straw etc.) and inorganic sources (silica gel, silicic acid, calcium silicate and potassium silicate) can be used for disease management.
- Thus exogenous Si application has a huge prospect in environment-friendly disease management.

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